

FOOD PRODUCTS THAT HELP FROM RADIATION.**Abdukadirova L.K¹****Jalolov N. N²****Akbaralieva G. Sh³****Tashkent Medical Academy****<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7841034>**

Ionizing radiation sources are widely used in the national economy and medicine. In the national economy, ionizing radiation sources are widely used in metallurgy, railway transport, chemical industry, geology (exploration), agriculture, scientific research and energy (NPP). In medical practice, the most common source of ionizing radiation is used in the diagnosis and treatment of the disease[1,2].

Sources of ionizing radiation are harmful factors, which means that those who work with this factor are among those who work in harmful professions.

Proper nutrition is one of the most important factors for those who work in dangerous professions. The provision of medical and preventive products to personnel working with ionizing radiation sources must comply with the "Principles of Labor Legislation" (Labor Code – Labor Code - 10–Chapter 177-section). According to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the fundamentals of labor laws", "It is necessary to provide milk and its equivalents free of charge in working conditions, as well as free of charge to provide therapeutic and preventive nutrition in the prescribed amount." Currently, the provision of medical and preventive services to persons working with harmful factors in the Republic of Uzbekistan is carried out on the basis of SanPiN No. 0051-96 [3,4,5].

Of course, the best way to protect against radiation is a way not to be in places where dosimeters determine an increased radiation background. Radiation is harmful, but is it possible to reduce the danger of its effects on the body? It is quite possible to do this with the help of nutrition and natural remedies, maintaining a healthy lifestyle.

In nutrition, you should focus on the use of an increased amount of vegetables and fruits containing natural vitamins, pectins, fiber, and other important nutritional biological substances. These are carrots, viburnum berries, raspberries, gooseberries, apples, bananas, black elderberry fruits, lingonberries, hawthorn, blackberries, sea buckthorn, eggplants, buckwheat, kelp, dried fruits (raisins, dried apricots, prunes), celery, plum, tomatoes. Plentiful drinking is useful[6,7,16].

It is advisable to slightly change the diet of food by adding foods rich in vitamins A, E, C, P, and group B. So, vitamin A can be replenished if you eat more fish liver, milk, egg yolk, butter, sour cream, cream, cheeses.[14,15]

The source of vitamin E can be crude vegetable oil, sunflower, corn, sea buckthorn, soy, rosehip oil. Carotenoids, which are also called precursors of group A, are found in carrots, sea buckthorn, pumpkin, rosehip, apricots, peaches, red pepper. As you can see, there is an orange-red palette of fruits and vegetables. Olive oil is also useful, it can be added to salads, drink beet juice for a quarter of a glass three times a day. Vitamin C is found in high concentrations in rose hips, currants, carrots, citrus fruits, green peas, dill, cauliflower. B vitamins can be replenished if you eat bread kvass, confectionery on yeast dough[8,9,10].

It is recommended to include condensed milk, processed and hard cheeses, beef and eggs, calcined bread in addition to the diet. When choosing vegetable products, you can pay

attention to vegetables and fruits rich in vitamins and mineral salts, such as apricots, quince, cherries, grapes, raspberries, cherries, parsley[11,19,20].

Trace elements, potassium and calcium salts are ionic competitors of radionuclides, so it is necessary to take care of their sufficient amount in the body. The trace element selenium has a special radioprotective effect. In the form of a pharmaceutical product, it is sold in pharmacies. After consulting with the attending physician, it can be taken as an additional therapeutic and prophylactic agent to increase the radioprotective capabilities of the body. The earliest symptoms of radiation exposure to the body are usually manifested by disorders of the hematopoiesis system. For their prevention, it is recommended to systematically include sources of heme iron in the diet (meat, liver, fish, shrimp), and also parsley, dill, celery, lettuce. Folic acid contained in green crops takes part in the process of hematopoiesis. Replenishment of the body's fluid is better provided by juices, vitamin drinks, bread kvass, tea. Green tea is considered a panacea for computer radiation, as it neutralizes the effect of computer radiation, thanks to the useful substances and antioxidants contained in tea leaves[12,21].

Onion and garlic contain phytoncidal substances, also helps to rid the body of the penetrated radioactive nuclides. Dietary supplements based on seaweed, such as chlorella, kelp, have a beneficial effect.

Among pharmaceutical preparations there is a group of radioprotective agents or radioprotectors, but they can be used only when there is a real threat of high doses of radiation that can cause radiation sickness. In normal cases, they should not be taken[13,17,18].

Now about the power mode. It is better to eat 4-5 times a day, so that most of the calorie content of the diet falls on the first half of the day. It is necessary to avoid excessively hot dishes that burn the mucous membrane of the mouth, esophagus, stomach. Fats are added to ready meals.

Thus, the use of therapeutic and prophylactic food products in the nutrition regime of personnel working with ionizing radiation sources will help reduce the effects of the harmful factor.

References:

1. Abdukadirova, L. K., Jalolov, N. N., Nozimjonova, M. N., & Narzullayeva, U. S. (2022). EVALUATION OF PRACTICAL NUTRITION OF PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC HEPATITIS.
2. Jalolov, N. (2022). Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda sog 'lom turmush tarzini shakllantirishning dasturiy platformasi.
3. Jalolov, N. (2022, April). Умумтаълим мактаблари бошланғич синф ўқитувчиларнинг саломатлиги бўлажак авлодни тарбиялашнинг асосий мезони. Республиканской научно-практической конференция "ДНИ МОЛОДЫХ УЧЕННЫХ".
4. Jalolov, N. N., Niyazova, O. A., & Khairullaeva, L. G. (2023). Studying the actual nutrition of students of technical institutions (uzbekistan, germany).
5. Salomova, F. I., Akhmadaliev, N. O., Sharipova, S. A., & Abdukadirova, L. K. (2019). Social Portrait, Conditions, Lifestyle and Health of Universities Professors of The Republic of Uzbekistan in Modern Conditions. *Central Asian Journal of Medicine*, 2019(3), 93-103.
6. Zokirkhodjayev, S. Y., Jalolov, N. N., Ibragimova, M. M., & Makhmudova, I. A. (2019). THE

USE OF LOCAL LEGUMES IN THE DIET THERAPY OF CHRONIC HEPATITIS. Toshkent tibbiyot akademiyasi axborotnomasi, (1), 64-68.

7. Абдукадилова, Л. К. (1999). Бир ёшгача бўлган болалар соғлиқ ҳолатига ижтимоий-гигиеник ва экологик омилларнинг таъсири. *кандидатлик диссертацияси*.

8. Абдукадилова, Л. К. (2019). ЭКОЛОГИК БАҲҚАРОРЛИКНИ ТАЪМИНЛАШНИНГ МУҲИМ ОМИЛИ-АТМОСФЕРА ХАВОСИНИ МУҲОФАЗА ҚИЛИШДИР. *Интернаука*, (5-2), 49-50.

9. Абдукадилова, Л. К. (2022). Хомиладор аёлларнинг хақиқий овқатланиши ва витаминлар билан таъминланганлик ҳолатини ураганиш ва баҳолаш.

10. Абдукадилова, Л. К. Она ва бола саломатлиги-миллат соғлиги. *Тиббий таълимда инновацияларни қўллаш ва интеграл маърузаларни такомиллаштириш-2016* 96-97, 3.

11. Абдукадилова, Л. К. Соғлом турмуш тарзининг гигиеник асослари. *Фан ва техника тараққиётида хотин-қизларнинг ўрни. Республика илмий-амалий анжумани маърузалар тўплами-2017*.

12. Абдукадилова, Л. К., & Абдуллаева, Ў. Я. (2019). ТОШКЕНТ ШАҲРИ КИЧИК ЁШДАГИ БОЛАЛАР ТАРБИЯЛАНАЁТГАН ОИЛАЛАРНИНГ ИЖТимоий-гигиеник ҳолатини ўрганиш натижалари. *Интернаука*, (5-2), 47-48.

13. Абдукадилова, Л. К., & Абдурахмонов, Б. О. (2019). РАДИОЛОГИЯ БЎЛИМИ ХОНАЛАРИДАГИ НУРЛАНИШ ДОЗА ДАРАЖАСИНИ АНИҚЛАБ БАҲОЛАШ. *Интернаука*, (3-3), 30-31.

14. Абдукадилова, Л. К., & Умирбеков, О. Д. (2020). Даволаш профилактика муассасалари радиология бўлими хоналаридаги нурланиш доза даражасини аниқлаб баҳолаш. *Интернаука*, (2-2), 68-69.

15. Jalolov, N., & Parpiboeva, D. A. (2017). Лечебное питание при хронических заболеваниях печени.

16. Абдукадилова, Л. К., & Умирбеков, О. Д. (2020). ДАВОЛАШ ПРОФИЛАКТИКА МУАССАСАЛАРИ РАДИОЛОГИЯ БЎЛИМИ ХОНАЛАРИДАГИ НУРЛАНИШ ДОЗА ДАРАЖАСИНИ АНИҚЛАБ БАҲОЛАШ. *Интернаука*, (2-2), 68-69.

17. Абдукадилова, Л. К., Иброхимова, Д. И., & Гуломова, Ш. Х. (2023, February). ВЛИЯНИЕ БЕССОННИЦЫ НА ПСИХОЭМОЦИОНАЛЬНОЕ СОСТОЯНИЕ СТУДЕНТОВ. In *Proceedings of International Conference on Educational Discoveries and Humanities* (Vol. 2, No. 3, pp. 151-155).

18. Жалолов Н.Н., Собиров О.Г., Кабильжонова С.Р., Имамова А.О. (2023). РОЛЬ ЗДОРОВОГО ОБРАЗА ЖИЗНИ В ПРОФИЛАКТИКЕ ИНФАРКА МИОКАРДА.

19. Жалолов, Н. Н., Нуриддинова, З. И., Кобилжонова, Ш. Р., & Имамова, А. О. (2022). Главные факторы развития избыточного веса и ожирения у детей (Doctoral dissertation, O'zbekiston Respublikasi Sog'liqni Saqlash vazirligi, Toshkent tibbiyot akademiyasi, Koryo universiteti "Atrof muhit muhofazasining dolzarb muammolari va inson salomatligi" xalqaro ishtirok bilan Respublika 9-ilmiy-amaliy anjumani materiallari to'plami 153 bet).

20. Жалолов, Н., Зокирходжаев, Ш. Я., & Саломова, Ф. И. (2022, May). Сурункали гепатит билан касалланган беморларнинг ҳақиқий овқатланишини баҳолаш. «Тиббиётдаги замонавий илмий тадқиқотлар: долзарб муаммолар, ютуқлар ва инновациялар»//мавзусидаги халқаро илмий-амалий конференция.

21. Закирходжаев, Ш. Я., Жалолов, Н. Н., Абдукадилова, Л. К., & Мирсагатова, М. Р.

(2023). ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ПИТАНИЯ ПРИ ХРОНИЧЕСКИХ ГЕПАТИАХ.

22. Зокирходжаев, Ш. Я., Жалолов, Н. Н., Ибрагимова, М. М., & Махмудова, И. А. (2019).
Сурункали гепатитлар парҳезтерапиясида маҳаллий дуккакли махсулотларни қўллаш.

